

AGRARIAN REFORM IN BRAZIL: PROMINENCE OF THE MST IN THE MITIGATION OF SOCIAL DISPARITIES IN THE COUNTRYSIDE

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Abstract

The present study aims to list the significance of agrarian reform in the current Brazilian conjuncture, in view of the plural perspective that this system presupposes linked to social movements that fight for the right to land. Among these movements, the MST emerges as a fundamental piece that paves the way for the dissolution of social injustices in the countryside, that is, this group assumes the prerogative of obtaining and dividing lands that do not fulfill the social function of the soil, thus aiming at the conquest and redistribution. of these areas that, for a long time, remain with debts speculating only the financial value when passing the years against the members of this and other acronyms that fight for the condition of producing, commercializing and subsisting through planting. In addition, it should be noted that the MST has a socio-affirmative agenda, in which, women, black people and people of different sexualities assume positions of leadership, dialogue and prestige, that is, the movement is plural, progressive and tends to break with patriarchal patterns still present in contemporaneity.

Keywords: Agrarian reform; MST; Disparities, Social justice.

Introduction

Agrarian reform in Brazil involves ideological, social and political clashes, which tend to permeate the movement of those who fight for the right to land. In this perspective, small social movements established themselves in Brazil, and joined a more expressive one, the Landless Rural Workers Movement (MST), in which political agents, democratically elected and, who assumed, social agendas, intensified even more the discussions and expansion of groups, unions and associations that demand the right over unproductive latifundia (DELGADO, 2014).

The paradigms represent interests and ideologies, desires and determinations, which are materialized through public policies in territories according to the pretensions of social classes. Through the paradigmatic resource, scientists interpret realities and try to explain them. To do so, they select a set of constituents such as, for example: elements, components, variables, resources, indicators, data, information, etc., according to their perspectives and their histories, politically defining the results they want to demonstrate (DELGADO, 2014, p. 42).

However, envisioning the conquest of these spaces is not an easy and peaceful task, since social movements, which aim at social justice in the countryside, face the truculence of the very figure of justice and large landowners, who even without offering the production and discharge of their land debts remain under the alignment of the perpetuation of power and real estate speculation, which can ensure financial advantages and expressive profit in the long term, to the detriment of those who require the use of the soil for production, income generation and wealth (MACEDO, 1995).

For the individual, social justice consists of observing the general ethical rules of economic activity, those of the profession and respect for tax laws. The individual's observance of social justice legitimizes his acquisitions and income. For the State, social justice means the establishment of a competitive economic order that allows the development of each and everyone, as well as affirmative actions that restore, whenever necessary, a minimum of equality of opportunities among individuals, sectors, regions, etc. (MACEDO, 1995, p. 75).

In line with what was mentioned above, there is still the stigma that members of the Landless Rural Workers Movement (MST) are bandits, rioters and usurpers of lands that belong to others and, therefore, are demonized in traditional media, such as on TV and in the most diverse other contemporary ones, which are part of the world wide web. What should be highlighted is that it is untrue, because in order for the former private property to be lost, the National Institute of Colonization and Agrarian Reform (INCRA)

pays a hefty indemnity equivalent to the commercial value of the land subsequently occupied (SILVA; MARIANO, 2020).

Veja also makes use of definitional arguments, when it attributes to the MST concepts such as “terrorist”, “vandals”, “criminals”, “bandits” and “daring”. This creates an MST identity with varied but approximate definitions that generalize the Movement's practices. In this way, this speaker makes choices when defining, taking into account what is of interest to him (SILVA; MARIANO, 2020, p. 105).

Concomitantly to this, the role of social networks in disseminating fake news, assumes an even more serious prerogative and displaced from the real history, which permeates this movement, it is worth mentioning the comments on internet forums that the MST is linked to communist ideologies, who intend to transform Brazil into a Venezuela, that is, with regard to the implementation of a dictatorship of the proletariat.

In this perspective, it is worth noting that agrarian reform does not remove land ownership and that the subjects who make up the struggle movements for it are only exercising a Constitutional Law, even if it seems controversial, that is, this means saying that these citizens act as solvents of the coronelista power that lives on in Brazilian society, in which many own nothing and remain on the margins of ills and social disparities, while a small portion of landowners see their fortunes increase due to monetary speculation of unproductive latifundia (BÔAS, 2012).

MST actions are always linked to illegality. The articles that make up the agrarian code of the Federal Constitution – a legal achievement – are systematically omitted by the mainstream press. Popular self-organization as a way of resolving the problems of the poor population, as opposed to a State set up to guarantee privileges for the rich, is always discouraged through the association of this practice with acts of disorder and arbitrary violence. There is an interest in disconnecting the causes of the movement from its actions, to prevent the reasoning that our actions aim at building an order that meets popular demands. Given the intersection of these data, we can see that the monopoly of the mass media by the elite is currently one of the main obstacles to the attempt of mass social movements to establish a productive relationship of politicization, awareness and engagement, with most of them of the poor population victim of the consequences of the system governed by the laws of capital (BÔAS, 2012, p. 158-159).

Therefore, this scientific article aims to understand the genesis of agrarian reform in Brazil together with the civil movements that make up legends of struggle for unproductive land, thus seeking social justice, as well as the nuances involved in the

process of mitigating social disparities in the countryside.

Methodology

The research was carried out through a bibliographic review process of a qualitative nature, in which articles relevant to the theme from the last 10 years were curated, eliminating those that did not enter the scope. In addition, basic books were also part of the making of this article, aiming at sedimentation in primordial theoretical sources.

Results

Agrarian reform is characterized as a political movement that encompasses the countryside, thus, the struggle for the right to land is linked to a civil society movement, which claims access to spaces that are suitable for planting and that are not fulfilling the social function which, in this case, is generating wealth and growth, in terms of the economy and also the very sphere that makes up society (FERREIRA; TARREGA, 2013).

In this way, the countryside plays a role in a dynamic with the interests of society itself, which means that production needs to come before land accumulation, because in this way, the social function of the soil will be in full force and the community will be benefited to the detriment of the particular goals of the ruling class, which pursue individualistic and self-centered ideals.

However, in Brazil, the discussion within the political sphere that leads to agrarian reform is very recent, which means that the growth of monopolies linked to land ownership is a problem that has been dragging on since the moment of the colonization of Brazil, in 1530. In this way, the representativeness of the great lords was given primarily through the tasks of the land and how many slaves they held in their powers (SOUZA, 2000).

In this, the contemporary advance of capitalism in the countryside, began to intensify in an even more cruel way a series of segregation, poverty and misery in the areas where this system of accumulation spreads. In this way, unproductive speculative

agribusiness further exacerbates inequalities in the countryside, and the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) does not in fact reflect the absence of the State and the ills imposed on the working class in the countryside.

However, understanding what agrarian reform actually is in Brazil has become a premise that involves rhetoric, contradictions and interests of those who do not admit the loss of absolute power over the land, that is, agrarian reform arises in the context of redistribution of land for those subjects who do not have access and, this, directly implies the breaking of the hegemony of the wealthy few, who perpetuate their significance in society by having hectares of land that do not fulfill the social function in their hands (STEDILE; ESTEVAM, 2012).

A legal imbroglio was created, as in another article of the Constitution it is determined that all large properties that do not fulfill their social function are subject to expropriation. This social function should be assessed not only in relation to aspects of production and productivity, but also those related to care for the environment and social relations existing on the property. Finally, aspects of attention to the interests of society as a whole (STEDILE; ESTEVAM, 2012, p. 154).

Therefore, it is noticeable that for the maintenance of power, rhetoric and fallacies are created and disseminated, so that they fall into the popular bosom, and the agrarian reform movement is seen by society as something that borders on criminality and rebellion, on the part of those who require fair distribution of unproductive land that does not fulfill its social function. For this reason, checking information, in the internet age, has become a task to be considered as a daily activity, aiming at elucidating, contrasting and understanding what is a fact or a mistake.

In face of this, the contradiction emerges in the idea that for there to be a redistribution of land in the countryside, the owner will lose ownership and receive nothing in return, which is a mistake on the part of the news published in the media, which put the militants in the place of land usurpers. What happens is that the National Institute of Colonization and Agrarian Reform (INCRA) offers compensation to the owner of the latifundia after the occupation of the MST, that is, the government agency subsidizes the viability so that this place starts to fulfill its social function (SILVA et al., 2016).

In this bias, the notion of latifundia is inherent in agrarian reform, as the latifundio is configured as a large agricultural extension belonging to a single person, who was once

known as a colonel, family or private corporation that, many times, do not tend to exploit extensive use of the natural resources existing there only to maintain its monopoly, thus intensifying the social disparity in the countryside linked to the segregating dynamics of capitalism, which still reinforces Brazil's colonialist policy even in the 21st century (FERNÁNDEZ, 2016).

However, the conceptions of latifundia cannot be seen only as the existence of expressive unproductive hectares, the land, even if on a smaller scale and, which also does not fulfill the social function, is indeed susceptible to agrarian reform, as there are subjects capable of make that area a pivot point for production, collective income generation and transformative involvement that respects the environment.

Starting from the premise of social disparity, it occurs as a consequence of the accumulation of wealth in the hands of a few subjects, and the land has historically been envisioned as an agent that guarantees power and status to those who are part of the top of the social pyramid of different civilizations, in England, for example, the practice of enclosing common land came under the control of a single man, from the twelfth century onwards, thus making it impossible for the poorest to have access and right to them, which fostered the deterritorialization of the peasantry, in which, in this system, relations from then on took place only through subservience (MORUS, 1997).

It is worth mentioning, the example of the Northeast region of Brazil, which, for a long time, was configured under the orders and excesses of the former colonels, in which the enclosure took place in a constant and limiting way to the producers that made up the family and subsistence agriculture, that is, power subjugates, separates and fosters differences between the rich and poor classes, and this is the movement that spreads in a more “subtly” and masked way in our present reality.

Thus, enclosures imply the creation of territories, which for Souza (2019) have their genesis established from the moment the power relationship is established, that is, when there is a socially constituted space and it has an owner who establishes borders under its guard, aspects tend to gain new nuances that pervade the property and, in this case, enclosures persist in contemporary times, as large estates are the physical and visual demonstration of power and its socio-spatial interrelationships.

Thus, man is capable of modifying, reformulating, ordering and establishing notions of power over geographic space, since the act of taking possession, deforesting,

enclosing and extending his power, through speculation, ratifies this entire process of concentration of wealth. , which opposes the rights of dignity of the poorest without access to land.

[...] the concentration of land, in line with the Brazilian economic development model structured in the countryside by agribusiness, is reflected in the different types of conflicts, structuring themselves territorially and suppressing the possibilities of access for poor populations in that country. The Constitution Brazilian Federal Law (BRASIL, 1988), in accordance with Law No. 4,504, of November 30, 1964, guarantees the right of access to land for all, which would guarantee, if this Law is complied with, the end of the use of violence to curtail the large mass of landless workers from traditional communities in the country (CAMPOS; BEZERRA, 2022, p. 114).

In this, capitalism emerges as a key factor in the maintenance of social disparities in the countryside, since the unproductive latifundium is a denoting element that can have greater future profits, instead of fulfilling its social function, which, as seen previously, is to produce and consequently contributing to the phenomenon of food insecurity that plagues Brazil (CARVALHO, 2013).

This concentration of income and wealth by capitalist companies in the countryside has been taking shape --- as in the colonial period, with the massive support of government public policies. Its businesses go “pari passu” with government businesses. And, this choice of political favoring by governments to large domestic and foreign private agricultural and forestry businesses not only compromises national food sovereignty, but at the same time contributes to accumulation via the spoliation of natural resources and the exploitation of the country's workers (CARVALHO, 2013 , p.1).

Moreover, the capitalist mechanisms are perceptible, as drivers of social inequalities in the countryside, because in the neoliberal perspective, concentrating wealth, through unproductive latifundia, is advantageous, as it tends to maintain the privilege and “name”, in front of society, which increasingly more prizes having, and this is one of the pillars that originate and raise the tangent data to social inequalities in the countryside.

In view of the deterioration of nature, in favor of the economic progress of a few, which is reflected as a consequence of land speculation, the central-west region of Brazil has been the contemporary stage of the problems that permeate the accumulation of land, areas that contain biomes such as the cerrado and even the amazonian forest, has faced the degradation of its flora and fauna, as civil agents and even the current government of

the president of the republic Jair Bolsonaro, through its ministers and through the Ministry of the Environment, has relaxed laws , which act completely against the harmony of nature, thus exclusively benefiting those who aim at the concentration of land to the detriment of a collective social agenda, which is despised by neoliberal policies (FERNANDES, 2020).

Furthermore, it should be noted that for the unproductive latifundia to gain even more space, biomes have been gradually devastated and, in this system, there is a loss of fauna and flora biodiversity, as this place is deforested, burned and cleaned. This tends to force the migration of animal species, which may not adapt to another ecosystem. That is, not only man loses, but also nature, which takes years to settle down and fulfill its primary function, which is to maintain life.

Certainly, the accumulation of capital is totally linked to the land, as this, historically, through human agents, ordered and reordered the space, and this did not happen differently with the latifundia, as the geographic space began to be transformed having in view of the subjectivity of the concept of place, in which deforestation and the implementation of enclosures that originate ownership are still protagonists of changes that do not fit a static alteration, that is, the actions of man that commodify nature move and are perceptible, just compare satellite images of a given area, for example (SANTOS, 2014).

The transformation of the whole, which is an integral, into its parts - which are its differentials, also takes place through an ordered distribution, in space, of the impacts of the Whole, through its variables. Actions are not located blindly. Neither do men. The same is true of institutions and infrastructure. This is the very principle of differentiation between places, producing specific combinations in which the variables of the whole are found in a particular way (SANTOS, 2014, p. 125).

In the popular imagination, influenced by “word of mouth” and even by the media, the Landless Workers Movement (MST) originates from the Northeast region of Brazil, which is characterized as a mistake. In fact, this movement had its genesis within the National Meeting of Landless Workers, in the State of Paraná, in the southern region of Brazil, in 1984 (NICÁCIO; NICÁCIO, 2022).

Another point, which fostered the conception of the MST, was the fact that in

1970, the South region, in particular, underwent a strong advance in technological aspects, which involved production in the field, that is, at that moment, the rural worker became impotent and useless, since manual labor began to be replaced by more modern machines that aimed at high productivity, to the detriment of the agricultural working class of small properties, which comprised, for the most part, family farming with more rudimentary techniques and less competitive (SERRA et al., 2016).

The military government opted to maintain the agrarian structure that already existed in Brazil and adopted the bases of the Green Revolution model. The regions that suffered most intensely, initially, were the South and Southeast regions and, a little later, the Midwest region. Firstly, there was a preference for monocultures with the aim of exporting such as soy, corn, cotton and rice (SERRA et al., 2016, p. 6).

In this way, the accelerated industrialization process in rural areas intensified the phenomenon of rural exodus, in which small producers sold their land to large landowners, thus increasing the concentration of land in the hands of the most fortunate, and the others migrated to other areas. Brazilian regions, seeking better living conditions, which often did not occur as idealized (MUELLER; MARTINE, 2022).

As a result, there was a strong expulsion of labor and the space for tenants, partners and, in general, small producers was greatly reduced, causing a strong rural exodus. Moreover, due to a combination of several factors, land concentration ended up intensifying. As a result of all this, during the 1960s and 1970s, almost 30 million people left the countryside for the cities, and another important contingent of migrants headed for the Amazon frontier (MUELLER; MARTINI, 2022, p. 409).

In this perspective, one can mention the urban growth of São Paulo, because with the exodus, which occurred in the countryside, migrant workers began to perform other functions, among them, those of construction workers, since the salary that allowed dignity was the target to be embraced. In this, the peasants broke their bonds with the countryside and helped in the construction, expansion and enrichment of the metropolises with strenuous manual work. However, the MST equipped itself with peasants who did not give in to liberal capitalist pressures, and began to claim the right to land, as they had the techniques and knowledge, but with the arrival and insertion of the ambitions of cumulative capitalism, they began to be segregated and victims of boycotts by the great lords of the countryside, which is why social justice is employed in this popular

movement, in which access to land is denied (FORCHESATTO; MORETTO, 2021).

In line with what was mentioned above, it is pertinent to visualize the power that emerges from the people and the rural working class, since many of the laws and rights were acquired through the process of resistance, resilience and revolt against the unilateral interests of the ruling class, or that is, in a democracy, public policies need to appreciate the appeals of the population, of the whole, but especially for those who are marginalized in the Brazilian structural system and who do not enjoy such rights guaranteed by the current Federal Constitution.

As noted in the text, the MST is a fundamental piece in terms of conquering idle land, so that agricultural production, income generation and housing can be used, since the settlements are home to families who, in addition to producing, they need a home. That is, this movement requires basic rights, which are guaranteed to all citizens by the Federal Constitution of 1988 (CARTER, 2010).

The 1988 Constitution authorizes agrarian reform and qualifies property rights in terms of their social function. However, most judges insist on applying the Civil Code's absolutist approach to property rights. This closed legal methodology criminalizes MST activists. However, in an important victory for MST lawyers, the Superior Court of Justice ruled in 1996 that land occupations aimed at accelerating reform were “substantially distinct” from criminal acts against property. Far from simply ignoring legality, Meszaros concludes, the MST has actively contributed to influencing debates concerning the nature and function of the law (CARTER, 2010, p. 77).

Among these rights, it is worth highlighting subsistence, in this way, the MST invests in family farming, which, in turn, brings benefits to families and also to the environment, since family productivity, for the most part, is organic and it does not depend on agricultural pesticides, as there is the implementation of agroecology in these geographic spaces, acquired through commitment and non-acceptance of the whims of the ruling class, even with the tensions that encompass this systematic (GILBERT, 2013).

In many ways, these tensions around land rights are nothing new, human history has evolved around these conflicts, as it can be argued that wars have always involved territorial disputes. There is also a close relationship between land use, access and ownership, on the one hand, and development and poverty reduction, on the other (GILBERT, 2013, p. 136).

However, it is not enough just to enter the latifundium, it is necessary to have financial investments, which allow the purchase of machinery, so that there is in fact the

beginning of the fulfillment of the social function of this soil, therefore, it is common that there are cooperatives within the settlements, because the work in association with the members themselves facilitates dialogue, a holistic and cooperative vision in mitigating problems and in what can be done to achieve the goal of that community (CHIARIELLO; FARID, 2013).

From the organizational architecture, the cooperatives develop production and management activities, adopting the isonomy of the partners regarding internal democracy and collective ownership of land and means of production, something stipulated since the encampment stage, therefore prior to the foundation itself of cooperatives. Collectivization made it possible for work to be optimized for joint production, which would be difficult if the option were made for the individual use of lots and means of production (CHIARIELLO; FARID, 2013, p. 56-57).

In this regard, it is important to emphasize the importance of the MST in celebrating socio-affirmative actions within its community, which means that blacks, quilombolas, women and people who are part of the acronym LGBTQIAP+ have significant roles, which are contemplated in different hierarchical axes, such as, for example, in leadership roles, which oppose the patriarchy present in other acronyms.

In this sense, building territorialities in the bowels of these movements, the socio-territorial approach becomes latent and the awareness emerges that one can have LGBT in the struggle for land, and that their presence is relevant in the necessary resistance for the territorialization of movements in the face of globalized capitalism in the Brazilian field (CHELOTTI; GOMES; FILETO, 2020, p. 71).

However, the role of the feminine was for a long time neglected and made invisible, in which women did not hold the leading role in the actions taken by this movement fighting for idle land. However, nowadays, the figure of the feminine has been raising new prerogatives and active voice in decisions, organization and militancy, which intensify the socio-affirmative actions of this group.

By affirming its fundamental importance for the construction of a project that opposes the capitalist and patriarchal development model, it ends up expressing a struggle that is anti-capitalist and anti-patriarchal as transversal in the struggle for social changes, receiving, in this sense, the adhesion of urban women, which, finally, are also recognized around the issues brought by women from the countryside and the forest, which means that the March, each year, has had a more significant participation of “urban women” (AGUIAR, 2016, p. 286).

Furthermore, it is necessary to understand that the MST is made up, for the most part, of black people, who claim their place and distance themselves from the marginalization imposed by the Brazilian elite, that is, the socio-affirmative mechanisms permeate the entire chain of the movement, and the black emerges as a driving force, regarding the search for dialogue, rights and no longer subversion to the whims of a society that denies its roots, in favor of a European standard.

What is interesting in Bahia is that the largest number of leaders are black, from national coordinators to regional, sector and brigade leaders. Most are black, but it is possible to notice that those who are located closer to Salvador, or take on tasks that always need to be in articulation in Salvador and with other urban movements, dominate the theme more properly (SOUZA, 2017, p.7).

Final considerations

The present work proposed to demonstrate the prominence of the MST, in a society that still maintains the remnants of classicist and elitist thinking about minorities. In this regard, it is not only necessary to highlight the positive points of this movement of struggle for idle land, through Agrarian Reform, a constitutional and legitimate mechanism, however refuted, criminalized and marginalized by society, which does not understand the magnitude and prominence of this movement coined in the region. South of Brazil.

In view of what was mentioned above, prejudices and rancidity are assigned to Northeasterners, through xenophobia. That is, in the popular imagination, the MST had its origins in the States that formed the Northeast region of Brazil, in this, the use of pejorative and criminal terms are directed to this population. Nevertheless, reactions on social media are one of hostility, contempt and deliberate attacks. Therefore, the movement has its support undermined and tainted by lack of knowledge in the era of technology.

However, the majority of the social fabric immersed in new technologies do not seem to make good use of them, because, as noted, the elaboration and dissemination of false information has taken over social networks and many individuals have firmly believed that the MST is a movement that intends to implement communism in Brazil, removing the right to private property and benefits that cover a small portion of the already wealthy population.

However, what is observed in contemporary times, due to the massive use of social media, is the criminalization of the MST against civil society, that is, the elite still maintains discriminatory and non-inclusive discourses, with the purpose of perpetuating power in the long term, for through the speculation of unproductive latifundia that do not fulfill the social function determined in article 184 of the current Federal Constitution.

However, combating fake news in contemporary times has become an arduous task with regard to the media that use research, sources and comments from “researchers”, which tend to an ideological political bias, which leans against Human Rights. Human, civil and constitutional to what suits the landless subject himself. In this regard, as highlighted in the construction of this work, projects full of legal apparatus try to perpetuate power in the hands of the ruling class, which puts the poor in dismay and profound retrogression.

In short, it should be noted that the MST is prominent in combating socio-spatial, gender, and sexual inequalities and also in what permeates the protection of nature, since its agricultural production methods value the non-use of pesticides in plantations, the that favors a dynamic of respect for the soil, rivers and air.

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